

TOURISM POTENTIAL OF THE TURKISH WORLD: PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES IN SOCIAL TOURISM FOR INDIVIDUALS WITH DISABILITIES IN TURKEY

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Abstract. *This research examines both the opportunities and challenges faced by social tourism services in Turkey for individuals with disabilities. Utilizing a qualitative approach and thematic analysis, the study involved semi-structured interviews with disabled tourists from Uzbekistan who visited Turkey for social tourism between 2022 and 2024. The findings indicate that while accessibility and transportation services are generally adequate in major cities, significant issues arise due to insufficient infrastructure in rural areas and natural tourism destinations. Participants provided favorable evaluations regarding the assistance from hotel staff and the overall quality of services. Consequently, it was determined that to maximize Turkey’s potential in social tourism, there is a need to enhance access infrastructure in rural regions and place greater emphasis on staff training.*

Keywords: *disability Tourism Services, Social Tourism, Accessible Travel, Barrier-Free Design.*

Аннотация. *В данном исследовании рассматриваются как возможности, так и проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются социальные туристические услуги в Турции для людей с инвалидностью. Применяя качественный подход и тематический анализ, исследование включало полуструктурированные интервью с туристами с инвалидностью из Узбекистана, которые посетили Турцию для социального туризма в период с 2022 по 2024 год. Результаты показывают, что, хотя доступность и транспортные услуги в крупных городах в целом адекватны, значительные проблемы возникают из-за недостаточной инфраструктуры в сельских районах и на природных туристических объектах. Участники дали положительные оценки помощи персонала отелей и общему качеству услуг. В результате было определено, что для максимального использования потенциала Турции в социальном туризме необходимо улучшить инфраструктуру доступа в сельских районах и уделить больше внимания подготовке персонала.*

Ключевые слова: *услуги туризма для людей с инвалидностью, Социальный туризм, Доступные путешествия, Дизайн без барьеров.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqot Turkiyada nogironlar uchun ijtimoiy turizm xizmatlari oldida turgan imkoniyatlar va muammolarni o‘rganadi. Sifatli yondashuv va tematik tahlildan foydalangan holda, tadqiqot 2022 va 2024 yillarda ijtimoiy turizm uchun Turkiyaga tashrif buyurgan o‘zbek nogironlikka ega sayyohlar bilan yarim tuzilgan intervyularni o‘z ichiga oladi. Natijalar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, yirik shaharlarda erishimlilik va transport xizmatlari umuman olganda yetarli bo‘lsa-da, qishloq joylari va tabiat qoynidagi turizm manzillarida infratuzilmaning yetishmasligi katta muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Ishtirokchilar mehmonxona xodimlarining ko‘magini va xizmatlarning umumiy sifatini ijobiy baholadilar. Ilmiy izlanish davomida, Turkiyaning ijtimoiy turizmdagi potensialini maksimal darajada oshirish uchun*

qishloq joylardagi erishimlilik infratuzilmasini yaxshilash va xodimlarni tayyorlashga ko‘proq e‘tibor qaratish kerakligi aniqlandi.

Kalit so‘zlar: nogironlikka ega shaxslar uchun turizm xizmatlari, Ijtimoiy turizm, Imkoniyati cheklanganlar uchun sayohat, To‘siqsiz dizayn.

Introduction

Tourism is not merely an economic activity but also plays a crucial role in enhancing social and cultural connections. Social tourism, in particular, aims to increase the participation of marginalized groups such as the elderly, individuals with disabilities, and low-income populations in tourism activities. The primary goal of social tourism is to facilitate individuals' integration into society by improving their physical, social, and psychological well-being [8]. In this regard, enhancing accessibility for individuals with disabilities, promoting their involvement in social life, and diversifying the tourism sector are significant objectives [5].

Turkey remains a prominent destination in this domain due to its historical and cultural connections and its proximity to the Turkic World. Shared attributes such as language, religion, and cultural heritage contribute to strengthening the tourism potential between Turkey and the Turkic Republics, particularly Uzbekistan [12]. Turkey's advanced infrastructure in social tourism presents an appealing option for disabled individuals from the Turkic World, offering accessible tourist sites, specialized services, and opportunities for social engagement [4]. However, challenges persist in the realm of social tourism in Turkey, particularly concerning transportation, accessibility, and infrastructural deficiencies, which are significant barriers to the participation of disabled individuals [10]. Additionally, there is a need for the development of adequate social programs to facilitate the inclusion of disabled individuals in social activities and their integration into society [1]. These issues are highlighted as the main obstacles preventing Turkey from fully capitalizing on its social tourism potential.

This study aims to explore the social tourism opportunities available in Turkey for disabled individuals and to analyze the primary challenges encountered in developing these services. The central research question is: ‘What opportunities does Turkey provide for disabled individuals in social tourism, and what challenges are faced in enhancing these services?’ Consequently, this research assesses the current state of social tourism in Turkey, evaluates the benefits for disabled individuals from the Turkic World, and offers recommendations for developing a more inclusive social tourism infrastructure.

Method

This study employed a qualitative research approach aimed at gaining a profound understanding of individuals' experiences, perceptions, and social contexts. The research utilized a descriptive and interpretative framework to analyze human behaviors. The case study method was chosen as the research design. According to Heale and Twycross (2012), a case study involves a detailed and systematic investigation of an individual, group, or community, providing extensive data on various variables [6]. This method was selected to thoroughly explore the participation of disabled individuals from the Turkic World in social tourism in Turkey, focusing on their experiences, challenges, and opportunities.

Study Group

The study sample comprised eight disabled individuals from Uzbekistan who visited Turkey for social tourism between 2022 and 2024 and engaged with the social tourism services available in the country. To gain insights into their tourism experiences, the research assessed their

personal experiences during their travels and their satisfaction with the social tourism services provided. The participants had diverse experiences regarding physical and social accessibility and possessed various types of disabilities. Selection criteria for participants included traveling to Turkey for social tourism and having a disability. To maintain participant confidentiality, each individual was assigned a code (C1, C2, C3, etc.), and personal details were not disclosed. This coding approach ensured anonymity while facilitating data analysis and presentation, allowing for a thorough examination of participants' experiences and satisfaction levels.

Data Collection

Data collection involved a comprehensive literature review and a desktop research method, utilizing secondary sources from online databases and libraries [11]. Academic articles and official reports related to social tourism and accessibility for disabled individuals were reviewed extensively. Additionally, data were gathered through semi-structured interviews conducted both face-to-face and online to capture the experiences of disabled individuals visiting Turkey for social tourism. Longhurst (2009) emphasizes that semi-structured interviews are effective for exploring complex behaviors, emotions, and thoughts [7]. This method provided detailed information on participants' satisfaction with social tourism services, the challenges they faced, their involvement in social activities, and their recommendations for improving social tourism services.

Semi-Structured Interview Questions

- How do you assess the social tourism services provided in Turkey overall, and what specific features influenced your choice of Turkey as a social tourism destination? What aspects drew your attention when comparing Turkey to other countries?
- To what extent did you feel included in cultural, entertainment, or social events during your social tourism experience? How did the available opportunities and accessibility features impact your participation? What factors were the most challenging or gratifying for you?
- How would you evaluate the physical accessibility of tourist sites, such as hotels, museums, and historical landmarks that you visited? Were the facilities like elevators, ramps, and wide doors adequate for your disability? What were the major accessibility issues you faced at these locations?
- How do you perceive the accessibility of Turkey's transportation infrastructure, including public transport, private transfers, and airport services? How well do you think transportation vehicles and terminals cater to individuals with disabilities? What were the main transportation challenges you encountered during your visit?
- How satisfied were you with the social tourism services provided? What is your level of satisfaction regarding service quality, staff support, and guidance? What improvements would you suggest for enhancing these services?
- How socially integrated did you feel during your social tourism experience in Turkey? How did your interaction with society, local residents, and other participants in social events evolve? What improvements could be made to enhance social participation?
- What were the most significant challenges you faced regarding accommodation and touristic services within the scope of social tourism? Were issues related to physical access, staff sensitivity, or facility arrangements adequately addressed? If not, in which areas did you encounter difficulties?
- What recommendations can you offer for enhancing social tourism in Turkey for individuals with disabilities? What improvements should be made in terms of infrastructure, transportation, social events, and staff training?

- Based on your social tourism experiences, would you recommend Turkey as a destination for other individuals with disabilities? Why or why not? How would you evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of Turkey’s social tourism services?

Data Analysis

For the data analysis, a thematic analysis approach was employed, which facilitates the systematic organization and interpretation of interview data under specific themes and categories [2]. According to Morin et al. (2021), thematic analysis is notable for its flexibility and broad applicability in qualitative research [9].

The interview transcripts were meticulously examined to identify themes related to disabled individuals' satisfaction with their social tourism experiences, the challenges they faced, and their recommendations for improvements. Based on these themes, the overall satisfaction of disabled individuals with social tourism services in Turkey was assessed, and the primary difficulties encountered were highlighted. Consequently, suggestions for enhancing these services were formulated.

Findings

The data collected in this study were analyzed using thematic analysis, resulting in the identification of four primary themes: accessibility, social participation, satisfaction, and encountered difficulties. Each theme provides a distinct perspective on the social tourism experiences of individuals with disabilities in Turkey.

Theme	Sub-Theme	Positive/ Negative	Contributor Comments
Overall Assessment of Social Tourism Services in Turkey	Rationale for Selecting Social Tourism Services	Positive	C1: “Turkey is highly appealing due to its rich cultural and historical heritage.” C3: “Participating in social activities was relatively easy in major cities.”
	Comparison of Turkey with Other Destinations	Positive	C1: “I selected Turkey because its cultural similarities to Uzbekistan made it a familiar choice.”
Engagement in Social Activities	Engagement in Cultural and Entertainment Activities	Positive	C2: “The tours organized at the art galleries were exceptionally well managed.” C7: “Engaging in social activities at music festivals was quite straightforward.”
	Challenges Encountered	Negative	C4: “During peak times, it became challenging to participate in social activities.”

Accessibility of Tourist Sites and Associated Challenges	Urban Accessibility	Positive	C6: “The hotel in Istanbul fully accommodated all of my needs.”
	Accessibility and Physical Barriers in Rural Areas	Negative	C4: “The hotel in Cappadocia lacked ramps.” C5: “The absence of ramps at the hotel in the rural area posed significant difficulties.” C8: “Accessing the bazaar and beach with a wheelchair was very challenging.”
Transportation Infrastructure	Public Transportation and Mobility Services	Positive	C3: “I encountered no issues with transportation.” C5: “Public transportation services were quite satisfactory.”
Levels of Satisfaction	Supportiveness of Personnel	Positive	C4: “The hotel staff provided excellent assistance.” C5: “The guides were very supportive and helpful.”
Suggestions for Improvement and Recommendations	Infrastructure and Staff Training	Positive	C1: “Ramps are notably insufficient in rural areas.” C8: “There should be an increase in inclusive training for staff.” C3: “I would strongly recommend Turkey as a destination.” C4: “Although I was generally satisfied, improvements in infrastructure in rural areas are necessary.”

The overall assessment of social tourism services in Turkey highlights the country's rich cultural and historical heritage, which contributors found to be a significant factor in its appeal as a social tourism destination. It was noted that contributing to social events was relatively easy, particularly in major cities. The cultural similarity between Turkey and Uzbekistan played a crucial

role in the contributors' choice of Turkey over other destinations. This indicates that Turkey is a compelling option for countries with strong cultural connections in the realm of social tourism.

Feedback on contributing to social events was largely positive. Contributors appreciated the various accommodations made for individuals with disabilities at events such as art galleries and music festivals, which facilitated their comfort and engagement. Nonetheless, some contributors reported challenges in contributing to crowded events, suggesting that additional modifications could enhance accessibility in such scenarios. Overall, the efforts to make social events more inclusive were recognized as a positive development.

Experiences regarding the accessibility of tourist sites varied. While major cities generally offered positive experiences due to well-suited infrastructure, such as accessible hotels in Istanbul, significant accessibility issues were reported in rural and smaller tourist areas. Contributors highlighted the lack of ramps in popular destinations like Cappadocia and difficulties with bazaar access for wheelchair users. These findings indicate a need for improved accessibility in rural and nature tourism regions.

Contributors expressed strong satisfaction with Turkey's transportation infrastructure, noting that public transportation and private transfer services are well-suited for individuals with disabilities, with no significant transportation issues reported. The accessibility of public transportation vehicles and the ease of reaching various locations were seen as strengths of Turkey's transportation network, supporting the country's social tourism sector.

Satisfaction with social tourism services was generally high, with contributors praising the helpfulness and sensitivity of hotel staff and guides. The staff's awareness of disability needs and their prompt responses contributed significantly to the quality of social tourism services. This positive feedback underscores the strong human element within Turkey's social tourism sector.

In terms of development suggestions and recommendations, contributors broadly endorsed Turkey as a social tourism destination but stressed the need to address infrastructure shortcomings in rural areas. Specifically, they pointed out deficiencies in ramps and accessibility arrangements in nature tourism regions, which created substantial difficulties for individuals with disabilities. Additionally, there was a call for enhanced staff training. While the staff were generally considered helpful, increased awareness and training in certain areas were deemed necessary. Addressing these issues could offer Turkey important opportunities to further refine its social tourism services.

Overall, Turkey presents significant benefits for individuals with disabilities through its social tourism services and accessible infrastructure in urban areas. The strengths in transportation, staff sensitivity, and cultural connections make Turkey an appealing destination. However, improvements are needed in rural and nature tourism regions. Implementing these enhancements could solidify Turkey's position in social tourism and provide a more inclusive experience for individuals with disabilities.

Discussion

The findings of this study indicate that while Turkey's social tourism services provide substantial benefits for individuals with disabilities, several challenges remain. Notably, issues related to access in rural areas and insufficient physical infrastructure in nature tourism sites have been identified. Contributors frequently highlighted the absence of ramps and challenges in wheelchair accessibility at popular tourist destinations such as Cappadocia. These issues underscore the urgent need for enhanced infrastructure in rural areas. Inadequate accessibility remains a significant barrier hindering the involvement of individuals with disabilities in tourism.

On the positive side, Turkey’s transportation infrastructure is generally well-regarded. Most contributors reported no difficulties with public transportation and private transfer services, which suggests that this aspect of Turkey’s social tourism infrastructure is relatively strong. Nevertheless, further research is necessary to improve transportation accessibility in rural regions.

The role of cultural awareness and staff sensitivity is crucial for the effectiveness of social tourism services. Contributors noted that the staff at hotels and tourist facilities were generally supportive and considerate. However, this level of sensitivity needs to be extended across all regions and facilities. To address this, it is recommended that more comprehensive training and awareness programs be implemented to enhance staff understanding of disability needs. As Turkey aligns its social tourism services with international standards and develops more inclusive infrastructure, future opportunities for improving social tourism experiences are likely to increase.

Conclusion

Turkey has emerged as a compelling destination for individuals with disabilities, particularly due to the social tourism services available in its major cities. However, to enhance the inclusivity of the tourism experience for people with disabilities, there is a need for significant improvements in infrastructure across rural areas and the widespread implementation of accessibility standards in all tourist locations. Strategic measures should focus on prioritizing the enhancement of infrastructure, expanding personnel training, and fostering international partnerships. For Turkey to fully realize its potential in social tourism, comprehensive accessibility standards must be established nationwide. Strengthening international collaborations and developing accessible tourism initiatives will further position Turkey as a more inclusive and accessible destination for individuals with disabilities.

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